

Cramer-Rao Bound for Blind Channel Estimation in Multi-Carrier CDMA Systems*

Daniel I. Iglesia, Carlos J. Escudero, Luis Castedo
 Departamento de Electrónica y Sistemas.
 Universidad de A Coruña
 Campus de Elviña s/n, 15.071 A Coruña, SPAIN
 Tel: ++ 34-981-167150
 e-mail: escudero@des.fi.udc.es

ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a study of the effect of considering codes larger than the spreading gain when estimating the channel in a MultiCarrier Code Division Multiple Acces (MC-CDMA) system. In order to perform this study we calculate the Cramer-Rao Bound (CRB) of channel estimators for a MC-CDMA system. CRB gives a lower bound on the error covariance matrix for a parameter vector (in our case, the channel impulse response vector) [5], and it gives a benchmark against which algorithms performance can be compared.

1 Introduction

Multi-Carrier (MC) transmission methods for CDMA communication systems [1] have been recently proposed as an efficient technique to combat multipath propagation [2]. MC systems split the transmitted digital information in multiple carriers and achieve high transmission speeds using large symbol periods. As a consequence, MC systems can simply remove the Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) introducing a short guard time between symbols and avoid the utilization of a channel equalizer. Although ISI is considerably reduced, MC-CDMA systems still suffer from Multiple Access Interference (MAI) due to the loss of orthogonality between codes caused by channel distortion.

A large number of existing techniques for MAI suppression require the estimation of the channel parameters. In this paper we will derive the Cramer-Rao Bound (CRB) of channel estimators for a MC-CDMA system. CRB provides a lower bound of the variance in a parameter estimation problem [5] and provides a benchmark against which the performance of estimation algorithms can be compared. Recently, blind channel estimation methods based on subspace decomposition have been proposed [3]. These techniques provide a good channel estimation with only a short data record because they are based on second order statistics, thus outperforming other blind channel estimation approaches. Nevertheless, these techniques cannot be directly applied

to MC-CDMA systems unless we consider codes larger than the spreading gain [4]. In this paper we will compare the CRB with the variance obtained from these subspace estimation techniques.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the signal model of a downlink MC-CDMA system using long codes and the subspace decomposition technique used for blind channel estimation. In section 3 an analytical expression of the CRB that gives a lower bound of the Mean Square Error (MSE) of the channel estimation is derived. Section 4 shows the results of some computer simulations to illustrate the performance of the theoretical analysis and, finally, Section 5 is devoted to the conclusions.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the i -th user modulator.

2 Signal Model and Subspace Decomposition

Let us consider a discrete-time baseband equivalent model of a synchronous MC-CDMA system with N users using pL -chip signature codes where L is the spreading factor and $p \geq 1$ is an integer number. Figure 1 plots the block diagram of the i -th user modulator. Since the code repeats periodically each block of p consecutive symbols, the j -th symbol in block n transmitted by the i -th user is termed s_{np+j}^i . Next, let us split the i -th user signature code in p consecutive spreading subsequences $c_{i,j}(k)$, $k = 0, \dots, L-1$ and $j = 0, \dots, p-1$. Therefore, the sequence of symbols transmitted by the

* This research has been supported by FEDER (grant 1FD97-0082).

i -th user is given by

$$v_{n,j}^i(k) = s_{np+j}^i c_{i,j}(k) \quad (1)$$

for $k = 0, \dots, L-1$ $j = 0, \dots, p-1$ $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$
The modulator computes a L -IDFT (Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform) of (1) to obtain

$$V_{n,j}^i(m) = IDFT[v_{n,j}^i(k)] = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} v_{n,j}^i(k) e^{j \frac{2\pi}{L} km} \quad (2)$$

This signal is transmitted through a dispersive channel with an impulse response $h_i(m)$ of length M and Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). This channel is shared by other $N-1$ users and the received signal is

$$X_{n,j}(m) = \sum_{i=1}^N V_{n,j}^i(m) * h_i(m) + r_{n,j}(m) \quad (3)$$

where $*$ denotes discrete convolution and $r_{n,j}(m)$ represents the white noise sequence with variance σ_r^2 . To recover the transmitted symbols, the receiver applies a L -DFT (Discrete Fourier Transform) to the received signal (3). Assuming perfect synchronization and a sufficiently large guard time between symbols, the resultant signal is

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n,j}(k) &= DFT[X_{n,j}(m)] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N v_{n,j}^i(k) H_i(k) + \Gamma_{n,j}(k) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N s_{np+j}^i c_{i,j}(k) H_i(k) + \Gamma_{n,j}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $k = 0, \dots, L-1$ and $H_i(k)$ and $\Gamma_{n,j}(k)$ are the DFT's of $h_i(m)$ and $r_{n,j}(m)$, respectively.

Rewriting (4) in vector notation we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{n,j} &= [x_{n,j}(0), \dots, x_{n,j}(L-1)]^T \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N s_{np+j}^i \mathbf{C}_{i,j} \mathbf{H}_i + \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n,j} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N s_{np+j}^i \mathbf{C}_{i,j} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{h}_i + \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n,j} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $j = 0, \dots, p-1$, T denotes transposition, $\mathbf{C}_{i,j}$ is a diagonal matrix whose elements are the L chips of the code corresponding to the j -th subsequence for the i -th user, $\mathbf{H}_i = [H_i(0), \dots, H_i(L-1)]^T$, $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n,j} = [\Gamma_{n,j}(0), \dots, \Gamma_{n,j}(L-1)]^T$, $\mathbf{F}$ is the DFT matrix and $\mathbf{h}_i = [h_i(0), \dots, h_i(M-1)]^T$. Arranging the p vectors $\mathbf{x}_{n,j}$ into a single vector of length pL , we arrive at

$$\mathbf{x}(n) = [\mathbf{x}_{n,0}^T, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n,p-1}^T]^T = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{C}_i \mathcal{H}_i \mathbf{s}^i(np) + \mathbf{\Gamma}_n \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_i$ is a diagonal matrix containing the pL chips corresponding to the code associated to the i -th user, $\mathcal{H}_i = \mathbf{I}_p \otimes \mathbf{H}_i$, with $\mathbf{I}_p$ equal to the identity matrix of size $p \times p$ and $\otimes$, represents the Kronecker product, $\mathbf{s}^i(np) = [s_{np}^i, \dots, s_{np+p-1}^i]^T$ and $\mathbf{\Gamma}_n = [\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n,0}^T, \dots, \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n,p-1}^T]^T$. The autocorrelation matrix of the observations vector (6), assuming statistical independence between users and noise, is

$$\mathbf{R} = E[\mathbf{x}(n)\mathbf{x}^H(n)] = \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i^2 \mathbf{C}_i \mathcal{H}_i \mathcal{H}_i^H \mathbf{C}_i^H + \sigma_r^2 \mathbf{I}_{pL} \quad (7)$$

where $E[\cdot]$ is the expectation operator, H denotes conjugate transpose and σ_i^2 is the i -th user signal power. Exploiting the eigenstructure of (7) and taking into account the orthogonality between signal and noise subspace, it is possible to obtain [4] the following system of equations

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{C}_d \mathcal{H}_d)^H \mathbf{u}_l &= 0 \\ l &= pN, \dots, pL-1 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ is a $M \times L$ matrix and subindex d represents the desired user. It can be shown that to obtain a good estimation of the channel parameters it is necessary to satisfy a condition for the value of p .

$$p \geq \left\lceil \sqrt{\frac{M}{L-N}} \right\rceil \quad (9)$$

where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ is the ceiling operation which rounds up to the next integer value. The solution to this system of equations can be found by solving a minimization problem using the least squares method.

3 Cramer-Rao Bound

In order to show the effect of considering long codes in a MC-CDMA environment, we derive the expression for the CRB that specifies a lower bound of the Mean Square Error (MSE) for an estimator of $\mathbf{h}_d$ (i.e., the channel parameters)¹. The CRB covariance matrix is the inverse of the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM). FIM is the covariance matrix of the score function which is the gradient of the log-likelihood function. The standard way of computing a CRB is described in [6], where the FIM is obtained considering as parameters to estimate: σ_r^2 , σ_i^2 , s_n^i , $h_i(m)$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$, $m = 1, \dots, M$ and $n = 0, \dots, T-1$ where T is the number of observed vectors (6). However, the complexity of this technique depends on many parameters and it is rather cumbersome. To simplify the CRB analysis, we only consider, as parameters to estimate, the components of the desired user channel, that is, the remainder parameters are considered as nuisance [5]. This approximation will provide a lower variance bound but still good to compare the performance of the new algorithm.

¹Note that we have considered the first user as the desired one.

If we consider a fixed number of independent observed vectors, T , we can assume a multivariate normal model, $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x}(0), \mathbf{x}(1), \dots, \mathbf{x}(T-1))$, $\mathbf{x}(n) : \mathcal{N}[\overline{\mathbf{x}(n)}, \mathbf{R}]$ where $\overline{\mathbf{x}(n)} = E[\mathbf{x}(n)]$. The joint distribution of the complex random sample is given by

$$f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}) = (2\pi)^{-MN} \det(\mathbf{R}) \exp \left\{ - \sum_{n=0}^{T-1} (\mathbf{x}(i) - \overline{\mathbf{x}(n)})^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}(i) - \overline{\mathbf{x}(n)}) \right\} \quad (10)$$

where $\det(\cdot)$ represents the determinant of a square matrix. Therefore, we can generalize the results in [5] to the complex case.

Let us consider a vector of real parameters $\theta = [\text{real}(\mathbf{h}_d^T), \text{imag}(\mathbf{h}_d^T)]^T$ where $\text{real}(\cdot)$ and $\text{imag}(\cdot)$ are the real and imaginary parts of a complex vector, respectively. The FIM associated to θ is

$$\mathbf{J}_{\theta\theta} = E \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}) \right)^T \right] \quad (11)$$

In order to compute the FIM, it is easier to represent it with respect to the vector $\mathbf{h} = [\mathbf{h}_d^T, \mathbf{h}_d^H]^T$ and to relate it with (11) as (see [7])

$$\mathbf{J}_{\theta\theta} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_M & \mathbf{I}_M \\ j\mathbf{I}_M & -j\mathbf{I}_M \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}\mathbf{h}} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_M & \mathbf{I}_M \\ j\mathbf{I}_M & -j\mathbf{I}_M \end{pmatrix}^T \quad (12)$$

Doing an analysis similar to [5, 7] we can obtain

$$\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}\mathbf{h}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d \mathbf{h}_d} & \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d \mathbf{h}_d^*} \\ \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d^* \mathbf{h}_d} & \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d^* \mathbf{h}_d^*} \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where the elements (i, j) of the four submatrices in (13) are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d \mathbf{h}_d}(i, j) &= T \text{Trace} \left[\mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d(i)} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d(j)} \right] \\ \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d \mathbf{h}_d^*}(i, j) &= T \text{Trace} \left[\mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d(i)} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d^*(j)} \right] \\ &\quad + \text{Trace} \left[\sum_{n=1}^T \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{x}^H(n)}}{\partial h_d^*(j)} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{x}(n)}}{\partial h_d(i)} \right] \\ \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d^* \mathbf{h}_d}(i, j) &= T \text{Trace} \left[\mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d^*(i)} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d(j)} \right] \\ &\quad + \text{Trace} \left[\sum_{n=1}^T \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{x}^H(n)}}{\partial h_d^*(i)} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{x}(n)}}{\partial h_d(j)} \right] \\ \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{h}_d^* \mathbf{h}_d^*}(i, j) &= T \text{Trace} \left[\mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d^*(i)} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d^*(j)} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Here $\text{Trace}[\cdot]$ represents the trace of a square matrix. Under our assumptions we can see that $\overline{\mathbf{x}(n)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{C}_i \mathcal{H}_i \mathbf{s}^i(np)$. For computing the FIM it is necessary to specify the value of the partial derivatives in

(14).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d(i)} &= \sigma_d^2 \mathbf{C}_d \mathcal{B}_i \mathcal{H}_d^H \mathbf{C}_d^H \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial h_d^*(i)} &= \sigma_d^2 \mathbf{C}_d \mathcal{H}_d \mathcal{B}_i^H \mathbf{C}_d^H \\ \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{x}(n)}}{\partial h_d(i)} &= \mathbf{C}_d \mathcal{B}_i \mathbf{s}^d(np) \\ \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{x}^H(n)}}{\partial h_d^*(i)} &= (\mathbf{s}^d(np))^* \mathcal{B}_i^H \mathbf{C}_d^H \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{B}_i$ is a $pL \times p$ matrix defined as follows

$$\mathcal{B}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{F}\mathbf{1}_i & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{F}\mathbf{1}_i & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{F}\mathbf{1}_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

As we saw before, by using blind estimation techniques using second order statistics, channel impulse response can be determined up to a complex unknown factor and, therefore, FIM is rank deficient. In order to avoid the ambiguity of the unknown factor and obtain the CRB, we saw before that we can fix one non-zero complex channel parameter, $h_d(i)$. Empirically, it was observed that considering fixed the channel parameter with largest energy [7], i.e., $\|h_d(i)\|^2$, it is obtained the minimum CRB. To fix this complex unknown parameter [6, 7] we must delete the rows and columns corresponding with the real and imaginary parts of it from the FIM before computing its inverse to obtain the CRB. In the simulations section we will show the CRB for a MC-CDMA in order to analyze the improvement obtained by using long codes. Moreover, this limit will be use to compare the results of the estimated MSE obtained with the algorithm described in [4] that exploits the advantages of the subspace properties.

4 Simulations

In this section we illustrate the effectiveness of the blind identification technique when using long codes by means of the study of the approximated MSE carried out by means of computer simulations. To compare the obtained expressions, figure 2 plots the CRB and the simulated MSE (averaged value of 20 realizations) with respect to the number of symbols for the blind channel estimation algorithm based on the subspace decomposition technique of [4]. An environment with 5 users, a spreading factor $L = 8$ and a channel length of $M = 5$ has been considered. The users are received with a Signal to Noise Ratio of $SNR = 20dB$. Note that when $p = 2$, i.e., condition (9) is satisfied, the simulated MSE is close to the CRB.

Figure 3 shows the CRB, with the same environment as before, for three different values of p . It can be seen

that for values satisfying (9) the resulting CRB is almost the same. However, for values not satisfying this condition the estimator will provide a lower MSE.

Figure 2: CRB and MSE for the algorithm in [4], vs. number of symbols ($p = 2$).

Figure 3: CRB vs. number of symbols for different values of p .

5 Conclusions

In this paper we have carried out a study of the validity of using codes larger than the spreading gain in a MC-CDMA system. In order to do this we derived the corresponding expression of the Cramer-Rao Bound that specifies a lower bound of the MSE of the channel estimation. In order to obtain the MSE, we have used a blind channel identification method for MC-CDMA systems using long codes which exploits the orthogonality between the signal and noise subspaces of the in-

coming signal. Then, we have compared this Cramer-Rao bound with the approximated MSE carried out by means of computer simulations, obtaining that the performance of this technique is quite good.

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